

Fig. D3. Morphometric PCA plot of nine informative flowering traits for sites in the CFP of California and Oregon with putative *C. howellii* in downward lavender triangles, *C. howellii* in purple triangles, *C. leichtlinii* ssp. *suksdorfii* in green diamonds, and *C. quamash* ssp. *breviflora* in blue circles (n = 300 plants, 3-4 sites/taxon). Traits in Appendix 2; sites in Table 1, Fig. 2 map. See also Fig. S6.